

SCOIR Model Institutional Open Access Policy [Version 2 post Consultation January 2025]

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Title	SCOIR Model Institutional Open Access Policy [Version 2 post Consultation January 2025]			
Description	<p>The SCOIR project is two-year project (2023-2025) funded by the National Open Research Forum (NORF). SCOIR aims to support the goal of 100% open access to publicly-funded research publications by adopting a two-pronged approach to policy and legislative change:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Develop a secondary publishing right for Ireland, drafting legislation in support of secondary publication rights based on an analysis of international and Irish law.2. Develop an open access policy framework for both funders and institutions that is aligned with the National Action Plan for Open Research and international best practice. <p>The project is jointly led by Trinity College Dublin and Technological University Dublin and is supported by a consortium of a wide range of partners and affiliates along with an international advisory board.</p>			
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Rialtas na hÉireann
Government of Ireland

This project has received funding from Ireland's National Open Research Forum (NORF) under the Open Research Fund Call.

SCOIR Model Institutional Open Access Policy

Purpose

[UNIVERSITY] is committed to ensuring equitable access to scholarly information for all, irrespective of location or technological or financial means and preserving the intellectual output of the institution.

Rationale

This policy facilitates the public benefit of open dissemination of research publications produced by [UNIVERSITY], in particular public funded research publications, and aims to maximise the reach of the work of our staff and students.

This policy is aligned with the [include alignment to institutional/university strategy], the National Action Plan for Open Research, a key pillar of which is open access to all research publications by 2030¹ and the UNESCO Recommendations on Open Science.² It also aligns with Plan S³, European Union's Open Science Policy⁴ and Horizon Europe's provisions on Open Science⁵.

Actions required by this policy

The [UNIVERSITY] endorses the National Action Plan for Open Research and requires 100% open access to research publications by 2030. The [UNIVERSITY] encourages all researchers to actively support and pursue open access initiatives and conduct open practices.

[UNIVERSITY] provides an environment to support its researchers making all of their research publications openly accessible through the institutional open repository (Green open access publishing), read and publish agreements, provision and support for Diamond OA publishing.

[The UNIVERSITY] will adopt workflows that respect researchers' autonomy and institutional intellectual property rights (as stated in the [UNIVERSITY's] intellectual property policy). These workflows will ensure that, at the latest, as soon as possible following acceptance for publication, an appropriate version of a research publication, such as an author's accepted manuscript or a version of record, will be made available in the institutional open repository with a Creative Commons licence or other suitable open public licence. These workflows operate outside the scope of existing copyright legislation. They ensure the version of the research publication published is not the version published by the publishers, unless they have provided a licence to the author for such publication, and thus does not infringe publishers' copyrights.

¹ National Action Plan for Open Research <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.ff36jz222>

² UNESCO Recommendations on Open Science <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science>

³ Plan S and Coalition S <https://www.coalition-s.org/>

⁴ European Commission, Open Science https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en

⁵ European Research Executive Agency, Open Science, https://rea.ec.europa.eu/open-science_en

The [UNIVERSITY] will, however, provide for appropriate exceptions and limitations to researchers' obligation with respect to this policy.

The [UNIVERSITY] will ensure that the obligation to make a research publication available does not apply where publication is precluded by another legal rule (such as national security or the GDPR), and it will acknowledge that an imperative reason of overriding public interest (such as, for example, academic freedom, the legitimate academic interests of the author, or the exceptional nature of a significant and substantial research publication) may permit the making available of the research publication to be postponed, but only for so long as is strictly necessary to satisfy that public interest.

It will be for a senior officer of [the UNIVERSITY] to determine whether such an interest has been established, and for how long any postponement should apply.

The [UNIVERSITY] will monitor and measure compliance with this policy regularly.

The [UNIVERSITY]'s platforms are developed and supported to align with the National Action Plan for Open Research and international best practices for open research. Through the implementation of standardised methods and protocols, standardised metadata is ensured for inclusion in global indexing and discovery systems, such as OpenAIRE.

All researchers at [the UNIVERSITY] are required to make their research publications immediately available open access without embargo via Green, Gold, or Diamond open access routes unless an exception as described above applies. Regardless of the chosen route, the author's accepted manuscript or version of record of a publication must be deposited in the institutional open repository as soon as possible following acceptance for publication unless a postponement described above applies.

Authors must include a statement on any publications explaining how other researchers can access any data, original software or materials underpinning the research, even where no data is associated with the publication.

Policy scope

This policy applies to all research publications produced by research personnel within the [UNIVERSITY], including full time staff, post doctoral researchers, Adjunct, Emeritus, visiting and contract personnel and research students officially engaged in research work at the university and undertaking any research activity in the [UNIVERSITY]'s name.

This policy does not apply to artistic, literary or other work not intended to constitute a research publication.

This policy applies to all research publications produced in academic, educational, innovation, intellectual, research, scholarly, scientific, technical, or other similar, contexts in [the UNIVERSITY], including, but not limited to, journal articles, conference papers, books, book chapters and reports, while recognising that open access publication routes are more established within some research disciplines than others and for certain publication types.

Provisos

This policy upholds the freedom of researchers to publish wherever they deem most appropriate while promoting the transition to open access publishing.

Support services

The university offers a range of support services to enable researchers to make their work open access. These include:

SELECT ALL WHICH APPLY

- the institutional open repository, Green route to open access publishing
- the CRIS system,
- access to IReL read and publish agreements,
- access to Diamond Open Access journals,
- access to open access initiatives (e.g. Open Library of Humanities, etc.)
- access to Publish, Review, Curate platforms (see glossary)

Date and review period

This model policy was developed in 2024 by the NORF-funded SCOIR project for adoption by Irish research performing organisations. It should be reviewed regularly as per standard institutional practice or at least every five years.

Glossary

Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM)

The version of the manuscript that contains the academically final text, but not yet the typesetting and formatting from the publisher. For scholarly articles in journals, this is the text after changes in response to peer-review but before the publisher's typesetting and formatting has been applied. May otherwise be known as the 'author manuscript', 'final author version' or 'post-print'. For chapters, this is the version of the manuscript that has been agreed for publication.

Copyright

A rights regime that grants exclusive rights to creators of original works, including literary, artistic, musical, and other creative expressions, allowing them to control how their works are used and distributed.

Creative Commons (CC) licences

A set of open licensing that grants rights under certain conditions and requirements, depending on the elements of each licence.

Diamond Open Access

The publisher provides immediate Open Access to the final published version on the publisher's website, but there is no fee for publishing. Diamond open access publications are often funded by organisations, institutions, or other initiatives.

Gold Open Access

Gold open access means the version of record of a publication is made freely available on the journal or publisher's website. Most Open Access journals do not charge for publication but some OA journals require authors to pay an Article Processing Charge or similar fee. The article is usually made available under a Creative Commons licence which facilitates reuse.

Green Open Access

Green open access is also known as 'self-archiving'. Authors deposit the author accepted manuscript of their article in an institutional or subject repository in parallel with conventional publication. Publishers sometimes require an embargo period before the file can be made accessible to the public.

Institutional repository

An institutional open repository collects, preserves and disseminates the research outputs of an institution. [All Irish Higher Education Institutions have their own institutional repository or access to an institutional repository].

Publish- Review- Curate

The publish-review-curate model integrates green open repositories, preprint servers, and diamond open access to enhance scholarly communication. Publishing involves making research accessible through preprints in green repositories and final versions via diamond open access. This can be on different or the same open infrastructure. Reviewing ensures research quality through transparent, expert peer evaluations. Curating focuses on organising and preserving scholarly content, ensuring its long-term accessibility and usability. This approach supports a sustainable and equitable open access environment.

Read-and-publish agreement

This is an agreement between the university and a publisher, where the University pays an annual fee that covers both the cost of subscription to the publisher's journals ('read') and the cost of publishing Gold Open Access in these journals ('publish'). This means that publishing Open Access in journals covered by such an agreement does not incur extra cost because these costs have already been paid for as part of the annual fee your library pays under the agreement. [Read-and-publish agreements are negotiated by IReL on behalf of a consortium of Irish HEIs].

Version of Record (VoR)

The published 'version of record' is usually a PDF that has undergone typesetting and has the publisher's branding on it.